

CLASSIFICATION OF TYPES OF TOURISM BY CHARACTERISTICS AND CHARACTERISTICS

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Annotation

This article describes the characteristics and characteristics of tourism types and organization features.

Key words: Socio-economic systems, tourism, complex internal structure, tourist services, sustainable development

With the increase in the service level of the activities of socio-economic systems, the volume and quality of the services provided in connection with the main activities of the production of products and the processes of work will become a factor of competitive advantage. With the expansion of the service process, the pace of development of structures within the service sector operating at the national and global level in individual countries and at the world level increases. One of such structures is the tourism sector and the industries within it, and as a result of the increasing needs of consumers for recreation and physical and mental recovery depending on the level of income, the sector is developing at a global level.

The field of tourism includes socio-economic small socio-economic systems, each of which has its own internal complex structure and goals, and they can move from one system to another under the influence of various changes. The analysis shows that the activity, which is considered the main subsystem of tourism in the world, is social, because it implements the right to rest, the right to freedom of movement, the right to spa treatment, the right to access cultural values and other basic rights.

Although all types of tourism services created in the industry do not have a material appearance like other services, they have a certain impact on the well-being, level and quality of life of the population. Tourist services have a number of specific characteristics that differ from other types of services (Table 1.1).

One of the important conditions for the sustainable development of the tourism industry, as mentioned above, is to achieve equal development of several other sectors related to the industry. Because the stable activity of the industry is closely related to the activity of certain sectors belonging to it.

Table 1.1
Specific features of tourist services

T/p	Specific features of tourist services	Tourist services are the essence of the features
1.	The fact that tourist services have socioeconomic importance at the same time	The social importance of tourist services is directly determined by providing employment to the population, increasing income, and increasing the quality and level of life. Its economic importance is directly determined by its contribution to the economy of the region and the country (GDP and GDP), its place in the service sector (share in GDP), production of tourist products, etc.
2.	Non-appearance in material form in the process of buying and selling tourist services	Tourist services, like other services, do not appear in material form in the process of sale, but are consumed at the same time. The service of the service provider, in accordance with his professionalism, implies the extent to which the consumer will be interested in this service and, as a result, depends on their overall level.
3.	Inability to maintain tourist services	Tourist services, like other services, cannot be stored, because they are consumed directly in the

		process of providing them, and their quality is also evaluated by the consumer in this process.
4.	Tourism services cannot be provided at the place of service and taken to another place	Tourism services are characterized by the fact that they are intangible, they cannot be stored and transported, and they are provided at the time and place of consumption and cannot be taken to another place.
5.	the simultaneous presence of the consumer, service provider and tourist product in the provision of tourist services	Another important feature of tourist services is characterized by the fact that the consumer, service provider and tourist product (service) must be present at the same time.
6.	Quality and competitiveness of tourism services	Enterprises and firms providing tourist services work in conditions of very high risk. If they fail to provide quality service, the chances of them losing out to the competition will be very high.

Types of tourism services are separated by separate classification signs and characteristics. In general, it is desirable to implement classification signs and characteristics within the framework of such signs as the territorial direction of tourists over time, the movement of tourists in a geographical direction, the form of organization of trips, and the sources of financing of trips (Table 1.2).

Table 1.2

Classification of tourism types by signs and characteristics

№	Classification marks	Types of tourism
1.	Territorial direction of tourists over time	Domestic tourism
		International tourism
2.	Movement of tourists in a geographical direction	Inbound tourism
		Domestic outbound tourism

		Domestic domestic tourism
		International inbound tourism
		International outbound tourism
3.	The form of organization of trips	Organized
		Not organized
4.	Sources of travel financing	Social
		Commerce

Domestic tourism has been studied by many foreign and local scholars and different opinions have been given to it. According to A. Kosolapov, one of the Russian scientists, domestic tourism is one of the certain segments of tourism that provides economic development of a country or region.

A. Trubshin said that domestic tourism is one of the types of tourism, which means that citizens of a certain country travel within this country.

By I. Tokhliev, it is distinguished from other forms of domestic tourism by the travel of citizens permanently residing within the borders of their country to a temporary visitor place (without paid activities) for tourist purposes, the travel of citizens permanently living in the territory of the country to other regions, domestic tourism crossing state borders and touristic with formality signs such as non-relatedness are highlighted separately.

Studies have shown that the economic organization of tourist services in general is possible only if there is a complex system of interaction of tourism industry subjects and objects that jointly create a tourist product, participate directly or indirectly in the process of production and sale of services. This rule applies in full when creating domestic tourism services (Table 1.1).

Tourism products are created and sold to customers through tourism enterprises that create tourism products on the basis of domestic tourism resources

and infrastructure and their connection within the framework of interactions of tourism industry subjects and objects participating in the process of creating and selling domestic tourism services.

The main tourist resources (education, entrepreneurship, treatment-health, sports and other areas) of tourist facilities are combined with infrastructure systems (accommodation, transport, food, recreation, etc.) through tour operators and a tourist product is formed. Tourist enterprises (tour operators and tourist agencies) form a tourist product, ensure its movement and organize the sales process.

The tourist product created in the market of domestic tourism services is tourist resources and tourist manuals that are formed by the tour operator taking into account the demand of domestic tourists and are promoted and implemented in the form of a tourist trip, the provision of guide services, transport services that ensure the movement of tourists, accommodation, food and health insurance services.

Today, in the countries of the world with high tourism potential, special attention is paid to the formation of tourist complexes by developing the tourism potential by combining it into a single complex. This shows that it is possible to use the touristic potential of our country initially in the form of domestic tourism complexes, and later (after the touristic image of the region is formed) to move to the international level.

As a conclusion, it can be said that the development of domestic tourism services in the market of tourism services, based on the generalization of the existing potential, expands the possibility of forming new tourist objects for the sector in a short period of time and bringing these objects to a new level.

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